

Note: This long-form article is an unpublished (as of October 2024) piece of work written in preparation for a much shorter and less technical co-authored chapter which appears in A Cultural History of Nature in the Modern Era (1920-today) Bloomsbury Cultural History of Nature, vol. 6. In the article below I explore the interplay of nature, mythmaking and religion across 20th century popular culture and the intertwined emergence of cultural anthropology as a field of study in that period through two case studies: witches and animism.

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Introduction

Non-human nature has formed a crucial part of origin stories, which often represent mytho-poetic attempts to provide coherence and boundaries to the human relationship with the surrounding landscape. This striving can be seen in the frequent reference to the earliest cosmological moments in myth as the initial expression of control by some divine being or beings over chaos, such as in Hesiod's recording of Greek myth in his *Theogony*, where Zeus is triumphant over Chronos. A similar arc can be seen in the Hebrew Bible, with a creation myth where God orders formless void into a cascade of flourishing life: first light and dark, water and land, then vegetables, animals and eventually humans. These narratives of ordering often project a vision of nature as wilderness, which is storied as requiring careful interaction in order to prevent harm to self and community. However, there are also pre-modern mythological depictions of the fragility of nature and the fraughtness of human interaction, often captured alongside the stories of human origin, such as the story of Prometheus who steals fire and is punished by Zeus and immortalised in the term "promethean". We can witness a similar range of alterities of nature across the modern period: from bountiful but dangerous medieval wilderness to protestant landscape management and conservation of vulnerable nature (cf. Berry, 2015; Stoll, 1997) and back again to the "revenge of Gaia" (Lovelock, 2007) described in the work of James Lovelock. There is ambiguity looking ahead as well, as environmental humanities scholars have begun to critically analyse and deconstruct the concept of "nature" (Carter, 2018) and that of "wilderness" (Cronon, 1996). We also begin to see ways that our cultural anthropologies may be experiencing queer critical forms of "re-wilding" or what Bron Szerszynski has described as "the End of the End of Nature" brought about by reflections on the Anthropocene (Szerszynski, 2012).

That there are two fundamental ways that new myth and ritual understandings of nature in the 20th century continue to be fashioned: (1) in the hermeneutical work of secular archaeologists and cultural anthropologists attempting to explain and reconstruct "discovered" societies (and in the process revealing implicit assumptions and projects of their own) and (2) in the formation of a wide range of new religious movements such as Eco-Paganism, Druidism, and Wicca. As I will go on to suggest, this process of meaning making is itself worthy of analysis as the past century in interpretation has had many dramatic twists and turns. Given this wide diversity this chapter cannot hope to provide a comprehensive survey of the range of mythologies and ritual engagements with nature. What I will aim to do is to identify some broad patterns among the variety of orientations which are possible and identify some models for how these understandings of self, nature and culture have been situated within mythologies and ritual systems. Though my survey in this chapter is concerned with cultural anthropology, my orientation also maps onto projects of comparative religious ethics which seek to provide a broadly pluralistic account which nonetheless attends to constructive and ethical implications of these systems and appropriations of them. My approach is also decolonial, so rather than provide a comprehensive survey of attitudes

towards nature in so-called traditional world religions, I will take a post-secular orientation towards religion. This basic orientation leads me away from conceptions of religion as a set of simple and easily compartmentalised religio-cultural groups (e.g. Islam, Buddhism, Christianity). Instead, I will attempt to account for the re-enchantment of nature as part of a broader post-secular shift. Carrying this pluralistic but constructive aspiration forward, my purpose in this chapter is also ethical, namely to observe what the challenges facing and options for a modern re-enchantment nature look like for the readership of this volume.

It is also worth emphasising that a post-secular approach to the cultural anthropology of nature will need to grasp at the more covert or unconventional ways that (1) modern societies mobilise forms of myth and ritual and (2) how critical theoretical frames regarding western adjacent or pre-modern myth and ritual orient ways of understanding the social function of myth. The latter of these two aims is especially relevant as critical theoretical work in cultural anthropology has developed approaches which are particular to the analysis of human-nature interaction. In my account, the usefulness of this diagnosis of modern work in cultural anthropology lies in thinking towards how we might continue to conduct this kind of work in a anthropocene reality where the tidy compartmentalisation no longer holds as a bulwark against the romantic trajectory that Isabelle Stengers describes as a “free and wild creation of concepts” (Stengers, 2011).

Given this delightfully messy state of affairs both in the theory, methodology and data caught up in the 20th century study of cultural anthropology of nature, I’m going to dive into the messy details of two particular domains: contemporary study and practice of (1) witches and (2) animists. I’ll provide a selective survey of these two fields in order to highlight different ways that nature and culture are brought together, and highlight some common themes and critical theoretical developments that will help me to, in concluding, observe some of the scholarly tensions and trajectories that carry forward to the present moment.

Witches

On 8 March 2022, for International Women’s Day, the first minister of Scotland issued a public apology acknowledging the “egregious historic injustice” which had been committed under the Witchcraft Act of 1563 towards thousands of women who had been tortured and executed by public authorities. This declaration and Nicola Sturgeon’s speech marked a profound shift which had been underway across the 20th and 21st century, repudiating acts of violence which inaugurated the modern period which stretched across Europe for two centuries. This act by a major political leader also underlined the maturation of a movement towards religious re-engagement with nature led by women which had been underway across the twentieth century.

Modern witchcraft and magic functions under a number of overlapping headings: Wicca (or “the Craft”), herbwifery, neo-paganism, druidry, Goddess worship, ecofeminism, ecopaganism and many more. It is also worth noting that part of the modern understanding of witchcraft has involved the redefinition of such as a form of “women’s work” (Millar, 2017, carrkelan_2021a). For the purpose of this chapter and our analysis of the cultural anthropology of ritual and myth in the 20th century, we will set aside parsing out the additional complexities of male witchcraft Green (2012), though the next section will look at overlapping forms of (also sometimes oppositely gendered) shamanism. In terms of its

definition as a religion, these diverse headings under which it occurs implicate witches under a broader definitional elusiveness in modern neopaganism. In observing this ambiguity, Michael York observes, “‘Paganism has no god’ and ‘paganism has many gods’” (York, 2009). On one hand, as he goes on to explain, there is an argument to be made that modern witchcraft is a form of “bi-theism. . . While names of deity and gods from Astarte, Ishtar, Demeter, Diana, Apollo, Mabon, Pan, etc. are often used and may even be individually worshiped, they are almost invariably considered to be instances or manifestations of either The Goddess or The God.” (York, 2009: 284). Alternatively, it can be said that modern forms of practice, especially those which are focussed on the recovery of the sanctity and vitality of nature in all its forms might also be seen as pantheistic or polytheistic. I’ll also discuss alternative forms of polytheism a bit more in the next case study, which deals with modern animism.

Many of these modern traditions see themselves as being involved in a task of cultural recovery and reconstruction, particularly in reaction to what is seen as a coercive limiting of religious practice in Europe to Christianity and an anxiety about the loss or suppression of non-Christian religions. There is a resulting effort on the part of modern practitioners both to recover ancient traditions, but also to work with these traditions in a kind of cultural improvisation. Given that this serves as a theme for animist practice as well, I will return to the subject of ritual creativity and mythopoeisis in the concluding section. This kind of religious playfulness is important to recognise not least because it seems to me to be an essential component in the process of greening/green religion. I will also go on to suggest that this kind of (potentially suppressed) theological play is intrinsic to all religious practice. This is significant in exposing underappreciated symmetries between monotheistic and polytheistic Green religion. In my view, the purified construal of Christianity as straightforwardly anti-pagan that one encounters in some 20th century scholarship misses internal diversity and playfulness within Christian, Islamic, Buddhist and other traditions (Kidwell, 2019).

In taking up comparative religious analysis, we might want to hold firm to a few convictions regarding the relationship between traditions. First, as the Scottish first minister highlighted, Christians were actively complicit in gendered acts of violence across Europe and repentance for these crimes has been nonexistent, delayed, or muted. However, the ways that narratives of persecution were configured can lead to a misleading dichotomisation in which a wide range of public figures and scholars are active participants. The actual relationship can be much murkier, and has been the subject of a long arc of anthropological speculation. To give one example, following scholars like James Frazer, Michael York argues that paganism might be seen as a “root religion” which means that “historically all other religions are off-shoots and/or counter-developments of the root religion. Consequently, if we wish to understand any religion, we must also understand paganism as the root from which it grew” (York, 2003, viii). These analyses have come under critique by scholars like Jason Josephson-Storm, not least for (as I will go on to observe further below) their problematic borrowing from early theories of social evolution. What I will suggest for now is that religions are not bounded ideological systems, but porous, and potentially interrelated or entangled in ways purified theoretical systems do not always appreciate. There is more at

stake in scholarly analysis of modern witchcraft than critique of androcentric doctrine, and recent scholarship has sought to recover the political and economic dimensions of the persecution of witchcraft and the ways that those dimensions continue to inflect contemporary practice.

This is the argument of Silvia Federici who suggests in her widely cited historical study, *Caliban and the Witch*, that “this is how we must read the attack against witchcraft and against that magical view of the world... eradicating these practices was a necessary condition for the capitalist rationalisation of work, since magic appeared as an illicit form of power and an instrument to obtain what one wanted without work” (Federici, 2004: 152). As Natasha Heenan observes Federici argues that “witch hunts, rather than representing the last dying breaths of feudal order and the attendant superstitions of feudal societies, were a tool to discipline and shape the emerging working class and hence were integral to the transition to capitalism.” [Heenan] Federici and the wider Marxist critical traditions that her study advances), sees these mythologies as serving as part of a broader structure of social control. While it is helpful to appreciate the broader context in which these movements and traditions unfolded, a possible outcome of this perspective is the possible instrumentalisation of religion, myth, and ritual, seen not in their own right, but as a small component part of a wider system. The critique of capitalism has also led a range of scholars to criticise and dismiss contemporary spiritual and new age traditions (cf. Heelas (2008)).

Modern Goddess mythologies

Keeping an eye on our ultimate goal in this chapter, which is to survey modern religious engagements with nature, I want to emphasise the ways that witchcraft represents a form of magical thinking and ritual creativity, which can (but may not always) function as a form of ecological reasoning. Seen in this way, we might say that magic, as a component of religion, depends upon some form of reflection and conviction regarding the human relationship to nature. This relationship to nature is not without ambiguity which I will note along the way in attending to tensions and gaps as well. For now, let’s begin with some attention to the role of mythology.

The ancient roots from which 20th century witches propagate contemporary mythologies are fragmentary and various. Potential mythological figures of note include the Greek and Roman goddess Hecate (also sometimes associated with the Babylonian Ereshchigal), mentioned in Hesiod’s *Theogony* (lines 411–52), and more briefly in a range of classical sources, such as Euripides tragedy *Medea* and Sophocles’s fragmentary play “*The Root Diggers*”. Accounts of Hecate are diverse, as Johnson relates, “modern worshippers embrace Hecate as a deity to be worshipped in one of two ways: as a bounteous and beneficent goddess reminiscent of Hesiod’s portrayal or as the figure of later times, namely the chthonic, threatening goddess of curses and dark crossroads” (Johnson, 2009: 314). Another ancient Goddess whose mythology is appropriated in modern ritual is Artemis (or Diana in Roman traditions), featured in Homer’s *Iliad*, Ovid’s *Metamorphoses*, as well as the anonymous *Homeric Hymn to Artemis* and Latin works such as Horace’s *Epode V*. In contrast to Hecate and Diana’s association with the powerful old crone and virginity, a third figure, Aphrodite has tended to serve as an “archetype of sexual energy present in modern Paganism” (Johnson, 2009: 326). Like the previous two, Aphrodite has been important for modern pagans as an individual figure of veneration and attention, serving as the inspiration

for the American Church of Aphrodite which was founded in 1938. In addition to these Greek and Roman sources, we also see Egyptian mythologies in wide circulation, particularly around the figures such as Isis and Serapis.

As I have suggested at the outset, modern witchcraft has varied widely in practice, and can in some cases focus in a straight-forwardly polytheistic way on specific figures (including those mentioned above), but it can also tend to be more of a free-form appropriation of different figures as “faces” of what is ultimately a singular Goddess. Luhrmann makes this argument in interpreting ethnographic data from her major study into modern witches in the following way:

The Goddess is multi-faceted, ever-changing - nature and nature's transformations. She is Artemis, virgin huntress, the crescent moon and the morning's freshness; Selene, Aphrodite and Demeter, in the full bloom of the earth's fertility; Hecate and axe-bearing Cerridwen, the crone who destroys, the dying forests which make room for new growth. The constant theme of the Goddess is cyclicity and transformation: the spinning Fates, the weaving spider, Aphrodite who each year arises virgin from the sea, Isis who swells and floods and diminishes as the Nile. Every face of the Goddess is a different goddess, and yet also the same, in a different aspect, and there are different goddesses for different years and seasons of one's life. (Luhrmann, 1989: 46)

As one can see from this account, these different mythologies provide anchors to specific features of nature, and by extension serve to facilitate attunement to those those shifting seasonal creaturely realities.

Primitive Mythologies?

The above examples indicate connections for modern mythologies to nature in their content inasmuch as a specific member of a pantheon anchors a divine nature of fecundity (e.g. Aphrodite), or decay (e.g. Hecate). We can also observe some important ways that mythologies orient by “form” that is, in the *attitudes* towards mythology and mythological creativity that they promulgate or support. The underpinning mythologies for contemporary witches can take on a revivalist aspect, in close and studied continuity with ancient traditions, but they can also function *ex novo* as novel contemporary mythopoetic creations. The revivalist account can be found in the subtitle of Starhawk's influential 1979 book *The Spiral Dance: a Rebirth of the Ancient Religion of the Great Goddess*. Early twentieth century work by folklorists such as Margaret Murray (sometimes referred to as the “Grandmother of Wicca”) suggested that reformation-era witches represented a wholly separate religion (“the Old Religion”) which had survived as a marginalised remnant of ancient forms of pagan practice alongside Christianity. Murray promoted the “Witch-Cult theory” in her outputs such as “The Witch-Cult in Western Europe” and in prominent publications such as her entry on “witchcraft” in the 1929-1969 editions of *Encyclopedia Britannica*. As Luhrmann suggests, “the ‘Murrayite thesis’ is rarely taken seriously, in its full form, today and historians of the 16-17th century have dismissed Murray's account of the”witch cult” (Luhrmann, 1989). However, it remains a key touchstone for the many lineage-based traditions and their offshoots in contemporary wicca.

In situating these lineage-based traditions in a wider context, scholars note how Murray (and others) were influenced by the Scottish folklorist and classicist James Frazer's 1890 book, *The Golden Bough*. Frazer's account, particularly in later revisions, is seen as

promoting an evolutionary account of the societal development which is resonant with Auguste Comte's law of three stages, written from 1830-1842 in his *Course in Positive Philosophy*. In looking for a way to guide societies towards positivistic (scientific) modes of operation, Comte argues that civilization proceeds through a succession of three stages, from (1) theological to (2) metaphysical finally giving way to a (3) positive (or "scientific") mode where the scientific method provided the underpinning basis for what he takes to be the most evolved form of human society. In a similar way, Frazer sees magic giving way to religion, and his theory in turn frames up the human relationship to nature. Frazer summarises his approach as the following: "we both hold that in the mental evolution of humanity an age of magic preceded an age of religion, and that the characteristic difference between magic and religion is that, whereas magic aims at controlling nature directly, religion aims at controlling it indirectly through the mediation of a powerful supernatural being or beings to whom man appeals for help and protection" [Frazer].

Frazer offers what Josephson-Storm describes as "the most significant early formulation of the disenchantment narrative in terms of the death of magic" (Josephson-Storm, 2017: 126). While one might be surprised to see that an advocate of secularisation and disenchantment is an important figure for modern witchcraft, the situation with Frazer is complex and worth some unpacking. In Josephson-Storm's analysis, the rise of British folklore is inextricably entangled with the development of colonial self-identity. This account resonates with work by other scholars who have connected the development of cultural anthropology as a discipline with the mission of the British foreign service to classify and understand colonised peoples for the sake of effective political control. As Josephson-Storm puts it, "To be a folklorist was therefore to study the superstitions of 'savages' as preserved in the world of the European peasant. If British anthropology was about objectifying foreign 'primitives,' folklore seems to have been preoccupied with the savages within the home islands, even as folklorists like Lang (and Frazer) gestured at the importance of studying both" (Josephson-Storm, 2017: 129). The benefit of studying so-called "local" (e.g. Irish or Scottish) folklore lay in "uncovering and exposing those superstitions that were an obstacle to modernization" (Josephson-Storm, 2017: 129). Equally, however, there were opposing traditions in the 20th century which saw local folklore as a form of "local cultures and traditions in danger of being lost by 'modernization'" (Josephson-Storm, 2017: 129). Whilst there are two seemingly opposed options, e.g. the preservationist and supercessionist options, it is important to underline that neither of these camps developed a suitably nuanced and realistic account of folklore (or ritual as we shall see below) and its social function. Instead, it served as a tool to advance different ideological programmes.

As I will highlight with the next case, there are alternatives to linear models of cultural evolution. Turning away from the lineage-oriented traditions which seek to show how contemporary practices are a faithful redeployment of more ancient practices, we can see a wide range of novel creative work at play in modern Wicca. For our reflection in this chapter, I'd like to highlight modes of creativity that can be seen in the formulation of hybrid religious identity. This is helpful in advancing a post-secular understanding inasmuch as these forms of practice call into question the ideological coherence of these traditions *in practice*. With this in mind, it is worth considering how theological playfulness can take us in unexpected

directions, including into forms of hybrid religion such as Jewish and Christian Goddess Spirituality (Beavis, 2015, lahav_2018a, raphael_1998a).

It is important to acknowledge that many contemporary practitioners do in fact construct their approach in contradistinction to adjacent religious traditions like Judaism or Christianity and in a similar way, many scholars argue that monotheistic religious systems like Christianity are antithetical to neo-paganism Martin (2005). However, a range of researchers have opened up studies of both accidental and deliberate forms of hybridity, blending seemingly opposed forms of practice in what Giselle Vincett calls “fusing”:

Fusers are interested in ‘holding together’. They exist in the joint, in the ‘and’, in the margins, and the edges where categories (that are usually treated as well-defined) blur. The apparently distinct worlds of Christianity and contemporary Paganism come together for the fusers to create a third thing. Some fusing participants of my study identify as Christian, some as Pagan, and others are consciously identifying as both, but all are strongly attracted to, and utilize elements of, both forms of religiosity. (Vincett, 2008: 159)

There is well noted tradition of Jewish eco-feminism, what Jill Hammer describes as “Jews Turning to the Goddess” which notably includes the influential figure mentioned above, Starhawk (Hammer, 2009, raphael_1998a). One can also find a range of examples where this has occurred in Christianity as well, including what Vincett describes as “Quagans” (Fusing Quakerism with Contemporary Paganism) (Vincett, 2009). One helpful outcome of this research has been the development of more granular assessment of the possible configurations in which practitioners can fuse religious practice. While it can seem odd or even controversial in the context of European religious practice to blend elements of cultural systems which contain contrasting or incompatible elements, this can be common outside the Euro-American context and indeed even within it as I have suggested with this case study here. Beavis suggests that this kind of syncretic, hybrid or “fusing” work represents an effort to (re-)enchant or reclaim Christianity (Beavis, 2015). As she observes, the pursuit of multiple religions can be ad hoc and accidental, but it can also represent a conscious choice by practitioners to engage in “complementary religious practice” (Beavis, 2015: 11). Michelle Voss Roberts, in identifying a range of different options for negotiating multiple religious belongings, suggests that “Hybrid identity is double because it affirms multiple realities; it is partial because it is never completely at home in any of them. The hybrid does not so much synthesize and resolve tensions between traditions as mark a place of difference within traditions, or a boundary in between traditions” (Roberts, 2010: 51). Seen in this way, hybrid practice like this points to a mode of inhabiting a series of traditions or cultural systems in order to reform or re-enchant them. This has some important implications for the ways that we might summarise the relationship between myth and ritual particularly in the context of greening or nature-oriented religion. As I will highlight in the final section, widening the array of theoretical options also presses us to think more carefully about the role of human agency in relating to nature. This can be a matter of working with an inherited tradition or cultural system or one of self-fashioning, but there are also many options in the middle. And as I shall explore in the next section, the ways that humans engage with nature

can also involve forms of co-design, perhaps even around forms of ecological ritual. With that in mind, I turn to my next case study, where we explore animism in the 20th century.

Animists

Like the study of witches, the cultural anthropology of animism also reveals a legacy of modern critical theory which has been substantially reconfigured, whilst also working alongside new local neo-animist social movements which seek to reappropriate these cultural resources in Euro-American contexts. I'll provide a bit of an overview of the way that theoretical work has unfolded across the 20th century, highlighting some of the ways that new ethnographies, particularly of urban animism, have put these early narratives about nature under pressure. I'll finish with an examination of the cultural re-appropriation of animism and neo-vitalism in new mythological and ritual formulations.

The study of animism was a core feature of early work in modern anthropology. As many 19th century anthropologists sought to parse the significance of discoveries in biology and Darwin's theory of evolution (*On the Origin of Species* was first published in 1859) for anthropological theory, there was a tendency to gravitate towards models of unilineal cultural evolution. This can be seen in work by Edward Burnett Tylor and his *Primitive Culture* where Tylor re-introduced the term "animism," which he defined as the belief in animals and other so-called "inanimate" parts of nature possessing souls. Prior to Tylor's redefinition of the term, it had been used by medieval and early modern philosophers in the sense of the latin *animus* to refer to a philosophical reflection on a general animating force and not to a particular form of religious practice. An additional innovation in Tylor's theoretical account was to define animism as the earliest stage of cultural development. As Lee Bailey suggests, "Tylor argued that animism is the childish, primitive, lower, savage origin of all 'higher' religions" (Bailey, 2014: 74). Over the ensuing decades scholars such as R. R. Marrett posed alternative theories regarding the most "primitive" form of religion, with an unresolved debate over whether polytheism was most primitive, or was actually preceded by a form of monotheism. Regardless of how one lands on this ongoing debate the notion that animism was a form of savage supersition proved persistent across the early decades of cultural anthropology. By the 20th century, however, this account fell out of favour and was decisively rejected. A key point of reference for this turn is E. E. Evans-Pritchard's book *Theories of Primitive Religion* (Evans-Pritchard, 1965). For much of the latter half of the 20th century, there seems to be a marked decline in studies of animism, but as scholars like Caroline Humphrey and Orgoni Onon point out, shamanism is often the other side of the animist coin, and the literature on shamanism can be seen as a proxy in those years for studies of animism, carrying forward seemingly abandoned research, and preferred by those later scholars for the ways that it enabled them to avoid the evolutionary and racial baggage of early 20th century animist studies (Humphrey and Onon, 1996). However, starting from the 1990s there have been several attempts to rehabilitate animism as a subject for the study of human-nature relationships in cultural anthropology, often referred to as the "ontological turn" which has arisen particularly from Amerindian studies and cultural anthropology of North Eurasian Pastoralists.

Re-Animating Nature: The Ontological Turn

Michael Watts suggests that “nature and culture are perhaps the two most complex words in the English language” and as such “their polarities are tangled, difficult and intractable” (Watts, 2005: 143). This presents a sometimes unacknowledged challenge to scholars studying both of these phenomena, including cultural anthropologists. The meaning, stability and coherence of the concept “culture” or “nature” is sometimes taken for granted in ways which intensify the ecological challenges we seek to confront and circumvent. Along these lines, a core issue which scholars of the “ontological turn” confront is the binary opposition of nature and culture and by extension the promotion of human exceptionalism, as this opposition often assumes that only humans (and not “nature”) can produce culture. This scholarship builds on earlier work in ecological anthropology and cultural ecology - by scholars such as Roy Rappaport and Gregory Bateson - which sought to acknowledge the connection between cultures and the natural environments in which they are situated. There are also links to the attempts of anthropologists such as Claude Lévi-Strauss who attempted to level previously assumed differences between so-called “savage” and “civilised” minds (Lévi-Strauss, 1966). One of the earliest proponents of the ontological turn, Philippe Descola, makes the case for this new paradigm in pointing out an irony within core anthropological theory, “those peoples who... have long been described as ‘natural’ are in fact as far as possible from the concept of ‘nature’ we have inherited from Plato and Aristotle, since they usually endow the plants and animals of their environment with many of the characteristics of social life” (Descola, 1992: 113). This way of thinking should be characterised, according to Descola, as fundamentally an ecological view. An important influence for this scholarship is the work of Philosopher Gregory Bateson who argued in 1972 for an “Ecology of Mind” which is not dichotomising, but attentive to a more holistic “pattern which connects” (Bateson, 1978). One of the popular aspects of the ontological turn in anthropology - especially for constructive scholars working in environmental ethics and posthumanist philosophy - is the emphasis on the particularity of the nature / culture dichotomy. However, as I will explore further below, indigenous scholars and critical geographers have since observed that, as Juanita Sundberg observes, “geographical engagements with posthumanism tend to reproduce colonial ways of knowing and being by enacting universalizing claims” (Sundberg, 2013: 34) By making claims that the nature / culture binary is pervasive and universal, scholars fail to recognise alternative indigenous counter-ontologies which are alive and well.

Given its influence, it will be helpful to unpack some of the key features of the ontological turn, and its attempt to reintroduce animism as a theme for anthropological study. Descola highlights the core emphasis in the culture groups being surveyed on relationship between different kinds of terrestrial beings. He defines it in the following way:

Animism is the belief that natural beings possess their own spiritual principles and that it is therefore possible for humans to establish with these entities personal relations of a certain kind—relations of protection, seduction, hostility, alliance, or exchange of services... It endows natural beings not only with human dispositions, granting them the status of persons with human emotions and often the ability to talk, but also with social attributes— a hierarchy of positions, behaviours based on kinship, respect for certain norms of conduct... Animic systems do not treat plants and animals as mere signs or as privileged operators of taxonomic thought; they treat them as proper persons, as irreducible categories. The relation of plants and animals to humans is not metaphorical, as in totemism, but at the most, and then only in certain cases, metonymic. (Descola, 1992: 114)

This movement is noteworthy as it represents a move by cultural anthropologists to take source material (particularly around forms of animist practice in the Americas) seriously on its own terms (Holbraad and Pedersen, 2017), and this “taking seriously” has highlighted the ethical salience of animist ontologies for a much wider audience across the humanities and social sciences. This can be contrasted with accounts which explicitly highlight the unreality of an accounted social world, as de Castro highlights, “when Evans-Pritchard found it necessary to warn his readers that ‘Witches, as the Azande conceive them, cannot exist’ (and then taking as his responsibility that of explaining to us why the Azande found it necessary to conceive things that cannot exist as we conceive them as existing)” (de Castro, 2015: 12). The Brazilian scholar Eduardo Viveiros de Castro, often described as another initiator of the “ontological turn” extends this account in an intersubjective direction in making a case for what he calls “Amerindian Perspectivism” (de Castro, 1998):

Typically, in normal conditions, humans see humans as humans, animals as animals and spirits (if they see them) as spirits; however animals (predators) and spirits see humans as animals (as prey) to the same extent that animals (as prey) see humans as spirits or as animals (predators). By the same token, animals and spirits see themselves as humans: they perceive themselves as (or become) anthropomorphic beings when they are in their own houses or villages and they experience their own habits and characteristics in the form of culture - they see their food as human food (jaguars see blood as manioc beer, vultures see the maggots in rotting meat as grilled fish, etc.), they see their bodily attributes (fur, feathers, claws, beaks, etc.) as body decorations or cultural instruments, they see their social system as organized in the same way as human institutions are (with chiefs, shamans, ceremonies, exogamous moieties etc.)... In sum, animals are people, or see themselves as persons. (de Castro, 1998: 470)

de Castro goes on to argue that this view is a “virtually universal Amerindian notion... of an original state of undifferentiation between humans and animals, described in mythology” (471). There are several key features of this scholarly account which are important to highlight for our study of nature, especially in mythical and ritual formulations. First, ontological thinkers are keen to present forms of animal life and other patterns in “nature” as forms of animated-animal culture in their own right. This impacts the way we might see animals as occupying an “animal” role in contradistinction to human “social roles, as de Castro suggests in the account above. Second, relationship forms a core emphasis of these programmes, as Viveiros de Castro suggests in his redefinition of animism as “an ontology which postulates the social character of relations between humans and nonhumans: the space between nature and society is itself social” (de Castro, 1998: 473). This new attention to animism has, third, enabled more fine-grained understandings of different forms of animism. In de Castro’s (2013) account, ontological (and by extension animist or totemist) systems carry different orientations towards several key aspects of reality: one can assume either continuity or discontinuity with regards to (a) bodily form (de Castro calls this “physicalities”) and (b) interiorities. As he suggests, “faced with some other entity, human or nonhuman, I can assume either that it possesses elements of physicality and interiority identical to my own, that both its interiority and its physicality are distinct from mine, that we have similar interiorities and different physicalities, or, finally, that our interiorities are different and our physicalities are analogous. I shall call the first combination “totemism,” the second “analogism,” the third “animism,” and the fourth “naturalism” (Descola, 2013: 121). A fourth significant element of this new approach is that, when they are taken as intertwined phenomena, we are forced to grapple with the ways that nature has an impact on human culture. This insight connects with earlier work in cultural ecology and may seem obvious in some ways, as our context is impacted by weather, seasonal rhythms, and so on. However, for urban citizens in the 1980s-1990s (and in many present day contexts), it might have been

possible to assume that one's daily experience can transcend reliance on "nature" and carry on with forms of theory and practice which produce a reification of wild nature (or "wilderness") as a place outside human culture as a "reserve" or conservation site. As Mark Woods suggests, "wilderness supposedly represents the quintessential non-human, natural world that, many argue, is deserving of our protection" (Woods, 1991: 350). The question which hovers over this animist renaissance is how it will pertain to an increasingly urbanised world, and we find an answer to this query particularly in the resonant work of cultural anthropologists engaging with North Eurasian pastoralists.

It is not surprising that anthropological engagement with North Eurasian peoples grew significantly after the fall of the USSR. Until the 1990s Euro-American scholars had little access to places like Mongolia or Siberia which were part of the USSR and behind the iron curtain. It is likely also that developments in cultural anthropology towards the latter decades of the 20th century were also enablers for a closer look at the role of shamanism and animism in Mongolia and Siberia alongside far-North Euro-American pastoralist and nomadic peoples in Sami and Inuit anthropology. Scholars have, in the last decade, begun to draw attention to the resonance with ontological turn theory, such as de Castro's perspectivism. To give one example Morten Pedersen argues for the occurrence of North Asian perspectivism. He points to the following account by an early Russian ethnographer, Jochelson of the Koryak of Far Eastern Siberia:

The bear, the wolf, the ermine, the moose, the raven, and other birds and animals, are described as taking off their skins and becoming men, and vice versa. Kllu', a niece of Big-Raven, put on a bear-skin and turned into a bear. Eme'mqut and his wives put on wide-brimmed, spotted hats, resembling fly-agaric, and turned into these poisonous fungi. Jochelson, 1908, p. 149, cited in (Pedersen, 2001: 421)

Looking to this account, Pedersen observes that "among the Koryak, humans can become nonhumans, and vice versa, by exchanging their own skin with that of their Others. You take on the skin of the bear and you become the bear. The bear takes on your skin, and it becomes you" (Pedersen, 2001: 421). Descola himself makes an attempt to show similarities across Amerindian data and that of Siberian ethnographies in order to demonstrate the universality of his perspectivist model (Descola, 2013: 366ff). However other scholars have attempted to highlight contrasts between these different cultural lifeworlds (see (Vaté and Eidson, 2021) for a summary). To give one example, (Willerslev, 2007) provides an account from his engagement with Yukaghir hunters of the ways that a strongly animist perspectivism might seem to pertain, but he also highlights ways that hunters seem to differentiate themselves from animals. Drawing on insights from mimetic theory, Willerslev suggests:

We can talk about a kind of 'depth reflexivity' built into mimesis, a certain withholding or nongiving of the self... The world of the Yukaghirs is, as we shall see, just like this. People here are betwixt and between: their souls are both substance and non-substance; they are both their bodies and their souls, their selves and reincarnated others; hunters are both humans and the animals they hunt, both predators and prey, and so on. This condition of fundamental liminality or in-betweenness seems to have no ending. People must constantly steer a difficult course between analogy and identity and tread a fine line between transcending difference and maintaining identity: they can and do transform themselves into various others, both human and nonhuman, but must avoid total participation and confusion. (Willerslev, 2007: 12)

Within the field of cultural anthropology, the ontological turn has not been without its critics. One important rejoinder has come from David Graeber, who himself has been a target of critique by Eduardo Viveiros de Castro (de Castro, 2015). Graeber picks up the reference

to Evans-Pritchard (noted above) and offers an alternative reading of that tradition and at the same time compares what are ultimately (e.g. his own and de Castro's) two inverted modes of response to radical alterity in anthropological analysis. As I have noted above, ontological turn theorists tend to prescribe a methodologically radical engagement with culture, seeking to preserve the "ontological self-determination of the other" but this rests upon the assumption of a possible universality of the theory on a meta level, and by extension, a constructive usefulness of this engagement with other worlds (de Castro, 2015: 11). As de Castro goes on to suggest, "Anthropology's role, then, is not that of explaining the world of the other, but rather of multiplying our world, 'filling it with all of those things expressed that do not exist beyond their expression'" (de Castro, 2015: 11–12). In contrast, Graeber defends his own position as one of "ontological realism with theoretical relativism" (Graeber, 2015: 3). For Graeber, theoretical *relativism* allows the anthropologist to seek points of connection with other worlds. Rather than "unsettling categories" so that we might "better understand the 'radical alterity' of a specific group of people", Graeber suggests that we might do so for another purpose: "to show that in certain ways, at least, such alterity was not quite as radical as we thought, and we can put those apparently exotic concepts to work to reexamine our own everyday assumptions and to say something new about human beings in general" (Graeber, 2015: 6). Graeber is earnest about his theoretical relativism, which can be seen in his final book *The Dawn of Everything*, co-authored with archaeologist David Wengrow and posthumously published (Graeber and Wengrow, 2021). In *The Dawn of Everything*, Graeber and Wengrow decisively refute unilineal models of cultural evolution and the underpinning commitment to an "original form of human society". Turning to some of the earliest archaeologically available accounts of human society and culture, the authors argue that even in ancient and pre-historic societies, there was a diversity of forms in political and social organisation. A key aspect of this argument is to dismantle notions of original primitive human innocence favoured by Rousseau and other Romantic thinkers. And herein lies the concern for Graeber, namely that "despite protestations to the contrary, OT does not abandon the traditional philosophical quest for a universal ontology, but rather proposes its own tacit universal ontology, which is essentially a form of philosophical Idealism" (Graeber, 2015: 3). Graeber argues for an approach, drawing on the ontological realism of Roy Bhaskar, "Rather than reject the notion that different theories or perspectives largely construct their objects, and are often in many ways incommensurable, Bhaskar argued that this was true—but it did not mean one needed to reject Ontology" (Graeber, 2015: 26). The result of this is that:

taking one's interlocutors seriously means, not just agreeing with everything they say (or even, picking out their most apparently strange or contradictory statements and trying to imagine a world in which those statements would be literally true) but starting from the recognition that neither party to the conversation will ever completely understand the world around them, or for that matter, each other. That's simply part of what it means to be human. Most of what obviously and immediately unites us across borders of every sort, conceptual included, is the recognition of our common limitations: whether that be the fact that all of us are mortal, or that none of us can never know with certainty how our projects will pan out. (Graeber, 2015: 27–28)

Graeber offers an alternative reading of myth and ritual and their relation to nature. His approach is not functionalist or reductive, but seeks pluralistically to find understanding across difference. His argument is that one finds a common sense of grappling with the paradoxical unknowns of everyday life. This in turn offers a theoretical position towards nature: "all of us are indeed faced with the stubborn reality—that is, immediate unpredictability, ultimate unknowability—of the physical environment that surrounds us" (Graeber, 2015: 28). Seen in this way, we might argue that de Castro and many of the ontologists emphasise the complexity of nature, whilst Graeber pursues a theoretical

emphasis on the complexity of culture. Ultimately, a major trajectory of all these theorists is to emphasise the necessity of recognising the intertwining of nature and culture. Seen in relation to religious orientations, the concept of culture proves especially problematic - are religions, and the concomitant forms of myth and ritual they carry, forms of culture?

Graeber's concerns about universality of claims resonate with another set of concerns by indigenous anthropologists and scholars, namely that in making reference to the spectre of climate change and the anthropocene, scholars can tend to make universal claims which ignore or even submerge counter-ontologies from indigenous scholarship (Todd, 2016). As Todd relates, we should be glad of re-engagement, especially in discussions of climate change where one can often find scholarly arguments that seem to resonate with Inuit, Aninishabe wisdom without any explicit ascription – forms of appropriation that look suspiciously like colonial patterns of resource extraction. Todd notes, “can a speaker be blamed for side-stepping a nod towards Inuit climate advocacy in a discussion of the ‘climate as common cosmopolitical concern’? Should I welcome his silence: better that he not address Indigenous thinking than to misinterpret it or distort it?” (Todd, 2016, p. 9). In contrast, the ontological turn, particularly seen in the earnest desire by amerindian and pastoralist anthropologists to take their subjects seriously, offers a counter example of ecological thinking arising from explicit engagement with indigenous and pastoralist cultures. However, here we encounter a different kind of problem in that scholars (like de Castro) can express a desire to establish a universal “indigenous” mind, which conceals uniqueness and difference among the underlying cultures and ontologies. There is a need to press this re-engagement towards less tokenistic engagements and towards more care-ful forms of engagement.

Along with Todd, scholars like Sarah Hunt, Max Liboiron, Juanita Sundberg and Vanessa Watts provide some helpful advice which can steer cultural study of animism towards celebration of all its complexity. This includes, as I have noted elsewhere, a willingness to engage in more self-implicating and personal forms of scholarship (Kidwell, 2023). Further, as Max Liboiron has argued, scholars can attend to more generous and expansive acts of attribution (Liboiron, 2021). One of my key points across all the case studies in this chapter is to highlight the importance and ubiquity of creative ritual practice (as I will note further just below), which is always iterating, evolving and expanding as cultures and contexts evolve. This stands in stark contrast to understandings of religion as a static phenomenon or as an top-down institution which shapes peoples lives (Kidwell, 2025). Appreciating creativity in practice and appropriation can also dovetail with an important extension of recognition towards indigenous scholars, which is to appreciate that those people are not, as Hunt (2014) observes, “past tense peoples” (p. 30, see also Henriksen, 2021). There are contemporary indigenous peoples, working with nature in unexpected ways, such as in urban animism. As Hunt suggests, “There is a danger in ghettoizing Indigenous geographic knowledge as ‘other’ or a curiosity, rather than engaging this knowledge in broader efforts to actively decolonize geography, navigating among differing power relations at the scales of both the individual academic and the broader discipline” (p. 31). Finally, against the universalising tendencies that Todd and Graeber find unsettling, we can pursue what Sami scholar Rauna Kuokkanen describes as “multiepistemic literacy” (cited in Sundberg 2013). This may imply taking up the kinds of pluralism (or something similar) to what Graeber calls for.

I noted in previous sections how the scholarly study of witchcraft has run alongside a resonant suite of eco-feminist practices and everyday cultural expressions. The same has been true for animist and shamanic traditions which have found expressions across a wide array of urban Euro-American cultural contexts, particularly since the 1960s (Townsend, 2004). The experiences and practices found in (post-)modern Shamanism have also been taken up of a growing body of research in folklore studies particularly since the 1990s (Adlam and Holyoak, 2005; Luhrmann, 2012). Space in this chapter doesn't permit a full treatment of this body of practice and ensuing research, so I will offer a few brief observations to highlight some of the broader issues at play. First, scholars have struggled to distinguish traditional from so-called non-traditional forms of practice. Part of the reason for this is because of the wide variety of styles taken up in appropriation, some heavily inflected by a concern for fidelity (as I have noted above with regards to ecofeminism) aiming to recover submerged versions of these forms of practice within local cultures, to faithfully re-deploy traditional knowledge for modern contexts. Joan Townsend makes an attempt to distinguish traditional shamanism from the "core" practice of Michael Harner and other forms of neo-shamanist practice (Townsend, 2004), on the basis of their lineage to specific practitioners. Other scholars highlight the levels of collusion between shamanic spirituality and forms of consumer capitalism. I find the purity tests lurking behind these forms of critique unsatisfying for several reasons. On one hand, they can rest on forms of what Said describes as "orientalising" or exoticising so-called traditional cultures in light of their difference from modern societies. This is unsuitable for analysis of animism because as the indigenous scholars I've just surveyed would observe, many of these traditional cultures have long since urbanised and "pure" forms of practice are a past and always problematic fiction. Urban anthropology, in the UK and USA and across a variety of pastoralist cultures which have also experienced rapid urbanisation, highlight the ambiguity around reconstructing traditions. There are some parallels between this appreciation of the messy everyday realities of the practice of nature religion or spirituality and the ways that urban geographers have also called into question the purity of rural nature against urban natures.

Conclusion

If we take seriously these problems of accuracy and fit in the use of purity tests and binary dichotomies for the study of nature and culture, there is a need to more closely attend to the particularities of individual cultural locations. What one finds there, particularly across the 20th century is a wide array of cultural and religious hybridities. Rather than dismiss cultural studies and forms of tradition re-appropriation, I have tried to open up a more expansive (if messy) inquiry into modern myth and ritual around nature. It's possible that this may also require some more authentic attention to our personal locatedness in light of post-secular forms of religion in setting up our theoretical postures. There's also a need to attend to forms of ritual creativity and mythopoesis, which are often a feature of modern interactions with nature both by cultural anthropologists and their research subjects.

The 20th century has seen a dizzying array of mythological poetics from a wide range of often conflicting and diverging sources and practices. This brief chapter couldn't hope to capture the full range, so what I've offered instead is a window into the ways that cultural anthropology has sought to situate and understand the dynamics of mythmaking and ritual craft in modernity through these two case studies. Against theorists who press for a

distinction between religion and magic (or indeed religion and spirituality), I would argue that a fundamental aspect of religious belief and belonging is creative appropriation of sources and traditions (for more on this see (Kidwell, 2019)).

I have noted along the way the underpinning critical theories and the ways that these create certain kinds of attention to myth and ritual, especially with regards to nature. As I've noted above, approaches like Tylor's assume (following a certain kind of Christian conception) that religious rituals express underlying beliefs and that religion (and by extension mythology) serves as an explanatory system. The same kind of characterisation occurs with regards to mythology. Here too Tylor, and other thinkers like Andrew Lang, treat myth as a kind of primitive science, by which one makes a child-like attempt to explain perplexing phenomena which occur in the natural world. As Justine Buck Quijada suggests, however, there are other ways of viewing rituals, particularly as "doing things, creating subjects and groups, and producing effects in the world" (4). On this alternative way of understanding the significance of ritual, we might see the purpose as being to establish and maintain social relationships, not just between humans, but with aspects of the natural world and the habitats that we live in. Tylor's approaches have been thoroughly (though not completely cf. (Stringer, 1999)) disavowed by cultural anthropologists, but this has not meant the end of the quest for a new metaphysic or ontology underpinning their analyses.

As I have noted above, we find ontological thinkers like Descola emphasising commonality, even foundations across a widely various dataset. It is important to appreciate that his account is construed in intentional contrast to a cultural ecology model. He observes early on, "it seems unlikely that these characteristics stem from their adaptation to a particular ecosystem that, thanks to its intrinsic properties, somehow provides an analogical model that makes it possible to work out how the world is organized" (Descola, 2013: 13). The main challenge to such a hypothesis (on his reading) lies in noting the shared cultural formulations with other animist societies, "elaborated by peoples living in a completely different environment, more than six thousand kilometers to the north of Amazonia" (Descola, 2013: 13). While there are points of distinction, as Descola argues, there is a shared inability to dichotomise nature and culture. Descola's programme, as such, is a constructive, even ethical one, pressing forward an observation around common humanity which challenges accounts of cultural pluralism in cultural anthropology which resist this kind of comparative dimension.

As I have hinted above, many of these anthropological studies veer away from neutral observation, indeed embracing forms of reflexivity which have become more common since *Writing Culture* even taking up research as a mode of constructive or ethical reflection (Clifford and Marcus, 1986). I have also pointed to movements of self-fashioning in which so-called modern societies attempt to reconstruct mythical and ritual systems. Renato Rosaldo writes about the ways that modern societies can come to see themselves as "People without Culture" (Rosaldo, 1988). What Rosaldo was pointing to was modes of cultural visibility and invisibility, but also ways that thick cultures had been submerged in the cultures-of-origin for many cultural anthropologists. Given that, as a long line of anthropologists have argued, the coherence of morality is embedded in culture and an

awareness of cultural heritage grants us the level of facility in perceiving ethics, this can place some scholars in the awkward position of being students of “culture” but not possessors of it. On another level, however, as Rosaldo suggests, the culture is *there* but submerged for various reasons. Modern Euro-American societies have disavowed, purified, narrowed, “recovered” and deconstructed to such a degree that what remains is sometimes mere ideology or pure affect but not a coherent moral system. The drive, seen across popular religious culture to appropriate religious systems with a jealous and hungry aspect, desiring to possess what they have through our current modes of possession and thus through consumption as individuals. While I am keen to commend forms of ritual creativity and mythical fashioning, there are some hazards lurking here we should be aware of.

These exchanges with other cultural systems where the relationship to nature is more visible - or *apparently* ethical - pose a challenge to contemporary study in light of nature and its decline. I’d like to argue that we are often engaged in work of refashioning culture. The study of culture can itself be part of this process of fashioning. Seen in this way, the study of culture has a strongly ethical component, identifying ways that people without (stories) history, overt mythology or culture can reconstruct one for themselves. This is the ethical task par excellence and a deeply religious one. It involves learning how to reconstruct forms of dwelling, awareness of place and modes of interaction without mimesis.

References

- Adlam R and Holyoak L (2005) Shamanism in the postmodern world: A review essay. *Studies in Religion/Sciences Religieuses* 34(3-4): 517–568.
- Apps L and Gow A (2003) *Male Witches in Early Modern Europe*. Manchester University Press.X
- Bailey LW (2014) Animism. In: Leeming DA (ed.) *Encyclopedia of Psychology and Religion*. Boston, MA: Springer US, pp. 73–78. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-6086-2_32.X
- Bateson G (1978) The pattern which connects. *The CoEvolution Quarterly*: 5–15.
- Beavis MA (2015) *Christian Goddess Spirituality: Enchanting Christianity*. Routledge.
- Berry E (2015) *Devoted to Nature : The Religious Roots of American Environmentalism*.
- Carter C (2018) Blood in the soil: The racial, racist, and religious dimensions of environmentalism. In: Hobgood L and Bauman W (eds) *The Bloomsbury Handbook of Religion and Nature*. Bloomsbury, pp. 45–61.
- Clifford J and Marcus GE (1986) *Writing Culture: The Poetics and Politics of Ethnography: A School of American Research Advanced Seminar*. Univ of California Press.
- Cronon W (1996) The trouble with wilderness: Or, getting back to the wrong nature. *Environmental History* 1(1). JSTOR: 7–28.
- de Castro EV (1998) Cosmological deixis and amerindian perspectivism. *The Journal of the Royal Anthropological Institute* 4(3). Royal Anthropological Institute of Great Britain; Ireland: 469–488.X
- de Castro EV (2015) Who is afraid of the ontological wolf? *The Cambridge Journal of Anthropology* 33(1): 2–17.

- Descola P (1992) Societies of nature and the nature of society. In: Kuper A (ed.) *Conceptualizing Society*. London: Routledge.
- Descola P (2013) *Beyond Nature and Culture* (tran. J Lloyd). University Of Chicago Press.
- Evans-Pritchard EE (1965) *Theories of Primitive Religion*. Clarendon Press.
- Federici S (2004) *Caliban and the Witch: Women, the Body and Primitive Accumulation*. Penguin Modern Classics.
- Graeber D (2015) Radical alterity is just another way of saying ‘reality’: A reply to eduardo viveiros de castro. *HAU: Journal of Ethnographic Theory* 5(2). doi: 10.14318/hau5.2.003. The University of Chicago Press: 1–41.X
- Graeber D and Wengrow D (2021) *The Dawn of Everything: A New History of Humanity*. Penguin Random House.
- Green D (2012) What men want? Initial thoughts on the male goddess movement. *Religion and Gender* 2(2): 305–327.X
- Hammer J (2009) To her we shall return: Jews turning to the goddess, the goddess turning to jews. In: Goldstein E (ed.) *New Jewish Feminism: Probling the Past, Forging the Future*. Woodstock, VT: Jewish Lights.
- Heelas P (2008) *Spiritualities of Life : New Age Romanticism and Consumptive Capitalism*. Blackwell.
- Holbraad Martin and Pedersen MA (2017) *The Ontological Turn: An Anthropological Exposition*. Cambridge University Press.
- Humphrey C and Onon U (1996) *Shamans and Elders: Experience, Knowledge, and Power Among the Daur Mongols*. Oxford University Press.
- Johnson M (2009) Drawing down the goddess: The ancient female deities of modern paganism. In: Pizza M and Lewis J (eds) *Handbook of Contemporary Paganism*. Brill, pp. 311–334.
- Josephson-Storm J Å. (2017) *The Myth of Disenchantment: Magic, Modernity, and the Birth of the Human Sciences*. University of Chicago Press.
- Kidwell JH (2019) Re-enchanting political theology. *Religions* 10(10).X
- Kidwell JH (2024) Personal knowledge: Teaching place-based religious ethics for our climate emergency. *Journal of Moral Education*: 1–12.X
- Lévi-Strauss C (1966) *The Savage Mind*. The nature of human society series. University of Chicago Press.
- Lovelock J (2007) *The Revenge of Gaia : Why the Earth Is Fighting Back - and How We Can Still Save Humanity*.X
- Luhrmann TM (1989) *Persuasions of the Witch’s Craft: Ritual Magic and Witchcraft in Present-Day England*. Oxford, UK: B. Blackwell.
- Luhrmann TM (2012) *When God Talks Back: Understanding the American Evangelical Relationship with God*. 1st ed. New York: Alfred A. Knopf.
- Martin D (2005) Secularization and the future of christianity. *Journal of Contemporary Religion* 20(2).
- Millar KM (2017) Toward a critical politics of precarity. *Sociology Compass* 11(6).X
- Pedersen MA (2001) Totemism, animism and north asian indigenous ontologies. *Journal of the Royal Anthropological Institute* 7(3). John Wiley & Sons, Ltd: 411–427.X
- Possamai A (2003) Alternative spiritualities and the cultural logic of late capitalism. *Culture and Religion* 4(1): 31–45.X
- Roberts MV (2010) Religious belonging and the multiple. *Journal of Feminist Studies in Religion* 26(1): 43–62.
- Rosaldo R (1988) Ideology, place, and people without culture. *Cultural Anthropology* 3(1): 77–87.X

- Stengers I (2011) *Thinking with Whitehead: A Free and Wild Creation of Concepts*. Harvard University Press.
- Stoll M (1997) *Protestantism, Capitalism, and Nature in America*. Albuquerque: University of New Mexico Press.
- Stringer MD (1999) Rethinking animism: Thoughts from the infancy of our discipline. *The Journal of the Royal Anthropological Institute* 5(4): 541–555.X
- Sundberg J (2013) Decolonizing posthumanist geographies. *Cultural Geographies* 21(1): 33–47.X
- Szerszynski B (2012) The end of the end of nature: The anthropocene and the fate of the human. *Oxford Literary Review* 34(2). Edinburgh University Press 22 George Square, Edinburgh EH8 9LF UK: 165–184.
- Todd Z (2016) An indigenous feminist's take on the ontological turn: 'ontology' is just another word for colonialism. *Journal of Historical Sociology* 29(1).X
- Townsend JB (2004) Individualist religious movements: Core and neo-shamanism. *Anthropology of Consciousness* 15(1). Blackwell Publishing Ltd: 1–9.X
- Vaté V and Eidson J (2021) The anthropology of ontology in siberia: A critical review. *Anthropologica* 63(2): 1–27.X
- Vincett G (2008) The fusers: New forms of spiritualized christianity. In: *Women and Religion in the West : Challenging Secularization / Edited by Kristin Aune, Sonya Sharma, Giselle Vincett*. Aldershot ; Burlington, VT: Ashgate.
- Vincett G (2009) Quagans: Fusing quakerism with contemporary paganism. *Quaker Studies* 13(2): 220–237.
- Watts M (2005) Nature:culture. In: Cloke P and Johnston R (eds) *Spaces of Geographical Thought: Deconstructing Human Geography's Binaries*. SAGE Publications, pp. 142–174.
- Willerslev R (2007) *Soul Hunters: Hunting, Animism, and Personhood Among the Siberian Yukaghirs*. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Woods M (1991) Wilderness. In: Jamieson D (ed.) *A Companion to Environmental Philosophy*. Wiley-Blackwell, pp. 349–361.
- York M (2003) *Pagan Theology: Paganism as a World Religion*. New York University Press.
- York M (2009) Pagan theology. In: Pizza M and Lewis J (eds) *Handbook of Contemporary Paganism*. Brill, pp. 283–309.